

The LuWang School, the School of Lu Xiangshan and Wang Yangming

By Johanna Liden, Stockholm university

Entry tags: Religious Group, Confucianism

Lu-Wang Confucianism is a part of Neo-Confucianism from the Song dynasty (970-1279) and onward. The main protagonists were Lu Xiangshan 陸象山 (1139-1192) and Wang Yangming 王陽明 (1472-1529). They reacted against the view of Cheng Yi 程頤 (1033-1107) and Zhu Xi 朱熹 (1130-1200), who shaped the so-called Cheng-Zhu Confucianism, a position which would become recognized as orthodox. Lu-Wang Confucianism is also called "The School of Mind/Heart" (Xinxue 心學 Learning of the Heart) and Cheng-Zhu Confucianism the "School of Principle" (Lixue 理學 Learning of the Principle). However, they are not isolated from each other. They manifested rather two different approaches in an ongoing debate. Zhu Xi and Lu Xiangshan met and were corresponding on philosophical matters. Lu Xiangshan is accused by the Cheng-Zhu Confucians for being a Chan Buddhist. It is his emphasis on spontaneity, criticism of textual and ritual rigidity, which lays behind such criticism. Such discrepancy is however found within the Buddhist tradition as well and even within Chan Buddhism. Therefore, this criticism does not give justice to the Lu-Wang current. It only reveals the vast span of Neo-Confucianism, their ideas, and praxis.

Date Range: 1200 CE - 1900 CE

Region: Ming and Qing China (combined area)

Region tags: China, Late Imperial China

The Lu-Wang practitioners were mostly active in the central parts of the country.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Ching, Julia, 1976, To Aquire Wisdom: the Way of Wang Yang-ming.

– Source 2: Chan, Wing-tsit, 1963, A Sourcebook in Chinese Philosophy.

– Source 3: Lü, Miao-fen 呂妙芬, 2010 , Yangmingxue shi ren shequn; Lishi, Sixiang yu Shijian 陽明學士人社群- 歷史、思想與實踐.

Reference: Ivanhoe, Philip J.. Readings from the Lu-wang School of Neo-confucianism. Hackett Publishing, 2009. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=Wk2dT22o19gC>.

Reference: Yao, Xinzhong, and Hsin-chung Yao. An Introduction to Confucianism. Cambridge University Press, 2000. https://books.google.com/books/about/An_Introduction_to_Confucianism.html?hl=&id=tAE2OJ9bPG0C.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://plato.stanford.edu/>

– Source 1 Description: The Standford Encyclopedia of Philosophy contains quite a lot on NeoConfucian philosophy

– Source 2 URL: <https://home.uni-leipzig.de/clartp/>

– Source 2 Description: The website of Prof. Philip Clart gives a useful bibliography on Chinese Popular Religion

– Source 3 URL: <https://bjterhaa.home.xs4all.nl/>

– Source 3 Description: The website of Prof. Barend ter Haar is a good complement to the one of Clart and gives other topics on Chinese religions.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org/>

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

Notes: Sometimes it is competitive.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: But sometimes there is debate and conflict.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: Within the Han Chinese area, it is rather neutral.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: In general not, but there was violence in the border areas and the Neo-Confucians worked there and tried to educate the non- Han Chinese people and teach them the Confucian classics and morality.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: They do not have violent conflicts with Daoists and Buddhists, but with people living in the border areas.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Sometimes they were organized in community compacts. In that case, they signed a contract of good moral behavior. This was not a membership list though.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

Notes: They did not have priests but the officials performed rituals so they still had a ritualistic function.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– Yes

Notes: The Emperor is both a political leader as well as the greatest ritual specialist. His sacrifice to Heaven and Earth stabilizes the world and cosmos.

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– Yes

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: The civil service examinations promote Neo-Confucian ethics. The examination questions are often essay questions on how to behave in a morally good way as an official.

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– I don't know

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– No

Notes: There is not a specific economic treatment of those belonging to the Lu-Wang School. As scholars and officials they are exempted from tax but that is not directly related to their religious and philosophical conviction.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: A person can of course become a Buddhist or a Daoist but they do not have to go through a special ritual for leaving Confucianism.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We know that those belonging to the Lu-Wang School mainly were officials, but we don't know the percentage of Lu-Wang adherents and the percentage of the more orthodox Cheng-Zhu adherents. Furthermore, we don't know exactly the number of officials in Ming and Qing China and the population of the country is a hotly debated issue. It is also a question of who we would call an official. Would we, for instance, call a clerk an official? Another way of approaching the problem would be to count the disciples of Lu Xiangshan and Wang Yangming respectively, which is not an easy task either. Huang Zongxi mentions 2005 scholars in his "Records of Ming Dynasty Confucian Learning (Mingru Xuean 明儒學案), but not all of them are disciples of Wang Yangming. Some of them such as Wu Yubi, and Chen Xianzhang lived before Wang Yangming. On the other hand, many more people participated in their organized activities in the private academies. How many is impossible to know.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– No

Notes: Some leaders are more active and prominent than others. Those people receive more disciples and followers.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– Yes

Notes: Beliefs in karma were quite accepted in the Ming and Qing dynasties.

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

Notes: Why certain people have more spiritual power is not always stated in the sources, some people just have it, but they certainly believe that you can increase your power by good deeds and they strongly argue for the benefit of doing good deeds.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– No

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Notes: As far as I know, there are no claims that the leaders are godlike. It even happened that they criticized the emperor which, however, could be dangerous. They would not point out the mistakes of Confucius and other ancient sages. That Wang Yangming criticized Zhu Xi was indeed very courageous, but within his own circles, the climate of the debate was rather open.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– No

Notes: A disciple seldom criticized his own master. That would be to go beyond his role as a disciple. If he was dissatisfied he would move on and choose a new master.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: As mentioned above, the debate was open and they would discuss different ethical and philosophical stances. The rituals would also be subject of debate.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– Yes

- ↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:
 - No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

- ↳ Are they written:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are they oral:
 - Yes

Notes: The scriptures are to a high degree memorized, and many practitioners learn them by heart without ever reading them. There are also oral stories, with edifying content which are told at meetings and gatherings.

- ↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:
 - No

Notes: No, there are no such stories as we are used to from Abrahamic religions.

- ↳ Are the scriptures alterable:
 - No

Notes: But there are discussions on which is the correct version of certain classics. Wang Yangming, for instance, questioned the new version of the Great Learning which was promoted by Zhu Xi. Instead, he advocated the old text version. Furthermore, which scriptures should be counted as classics have been under debate and, as time passed by, more classics were added to the corpus.

- ↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:
 - Yes

- ↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:
 - Yes

Notes: Interpretations were done by the officials educated in the civil service

examination system. Candidates for the examinations had to do their own interpretations and/or comment on others' interpretations. Students, for instance, had to comment on Zhu Xi's interpretation (after 1313 when his comments became compulsory reading) but they did not necessarily have to agree with him.

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– No

Notes: The founder of the Taizhou founder, Wang Gen (1483-1541) was a commoner without a degree from the civil examinations. He made his own interpretations, which were rather creative and non-conformist. Many scholars criticized him but surprisingly he was never persecuted for doing it.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The officials trained in reading the classics and whose knowledge was confirmed by successfully passing the examinations.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: Tombs of important figures were sites visited not only by descendants but also by other practitioners. The tomb of Confucius played of course a special role, but also his disciples such as the tomb of Yan Hui, the favorite disciple of Confucius.

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Notes: Charitable projects set up by philanthropic Neo-Confucians included cemeteries for those who did not have funding to buy land for their graves. Those were however not any buildings but usually a mound of soil.

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: Confucian temples were found in the whole country. The temples could be built within a school compound, but more often the other way around, that is, that there was a school within the temple compound.

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: If there was an independent school without a temple there would be an altar inside the school with a tablet representing Confucius to which incense was offered.

↳ Devotional markers:

– No

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– No

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Academy buildings

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: However, the question is under debate. Zhu Xi disliked images and sculptures of Confucius claiming it was a Buddhist tradition alien to Confucianism. He argued for using tablets with the name of Confucius instead. Other prominent Ming officials such as Qiu Jun 丘濬 (1421-1495) agreed on this view. However, the descendants of Confucius could use images. It seems as if this view was established in most cases. The Lu-Wang practitioners might have had a different view from that of the Cheng-Zhu adherents, but since the Cheng-Zhu school was regarded as orthodox by the state it probably was dominant.

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– No

Notes: As far as I know, the iconography of this particular group is not different from other Neo-Confucians although it was Zhu Xi who had argued for replacing statues and images of Confucius with tablets. In 1530, the Jiajing emperor decided to prohibit statues of Confucius in

all temples in China except for in the Qufu temple which belonged to the descendants of Confucius. However, it seems as if the printing boom in the Ming dynasty made the printing of Confucius images more common among ordinary people.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Notes: Temples and pagodas are very often built on mountains and other specific sites but the Confucian temples are more linked to culture than nature and therefore more connected with schools, academies and higher educational institutions.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: A visit to the Confucian temple in Qufu could be regarded as a pilgrimage tour. The emperor would try to travel there at least once during their reign period. Other Neo-Confucians often did the same.

How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

– I don't know

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– No

Notes: The spirit body distinction in Chinese traditional culture is not very distinct. The concept of mind is a big issue and deserves an article or book in itself. First of all, the Chinese word for mind 'xin' 心 originally had the meaning 'heart'. However, the Chinese believed the conscience was in the heart so the meaning of 'conscience' was added to it. When Buddhism came to China, they used the word 'xin' to translate the Sanskrit word 'citta'. Some Western scholars, therefore, use the compound heart-mind to translate 'xin'. In NeoConfucian philosophy, the dichotomy spirit - body is rare - I cannot remember I have seen it at all. What they talk about is 'xin' and 'qi' 氣, which could be translated as 'vital force',

'psychophysical stuff' and so on. 'Qi' is both what we in the West regard as spiritual and physical. It is a kind of energy, or the interface between our bodies and spiritual self. It is the Chinese equivalent of the Sanskrit word 'prana' and the Greek word 'pneuma'.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Notes: The leading figures of the LuWang School does not talk much about afterlife. An undisturbed state of mind is the most important question for them. I would, however, not be surprised if not only less philosophical-minded practitioners within the movement believed that the soul of a person enters the underworld after death. Furthermore, belief in karma had in the Ming dynasty (1368-1644) become common no matter if you were a Confucian, a Daoist or a Buddhist.

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form:

– Yes

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– I don't know

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

Notes: The idea of karma was transmitted by Buddhist teaching to China and became an essential part of their beliefs.

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– I don't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: Zhu Xi mentions in his "Family Rituals" that guests should bring objects of sacrifice to the grave. The presiding mourner "gives six pieces of black cloth and four of crimson, each eighteen feet long" (Chu Hsi 1991: 121). According to Zhu Xi, gold and jade should not be put in the grave since such objects would be a burden for the dead. Inscription stones were often buried in the same vault as the coffin (Chu Hsi 1991: 122).

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: Probably, yes.

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: As mentioned above, inscriptions stones were placed in the grave. That Zhu Xi argued against putting jade and gold might be because that in fact was rather common in the Song dynasty.

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

Notes: Archeological excavations of tombs show that copper coins, stone figurines, porcelain, bronze/iron mirrors, ink stones, epitaphs and so on were common grave objects. The gifts should be personal.

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Notes: Such as silk.

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Yes [specify]: For the emperor, and possibly also for high officials, the posthumous name was inscribed on a tablet made of wood or jade. This tablet was placed in the grave beside the coffin.

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Notes: Food is a common gift in front of the ancestral altar, at the tomb as well as in the grave. In the grave, the food offered were usually dried items.

Reference: Rawski, Evelyn S.. "the Imperial Way of Death", In: *Death Ritual in Late Imperial and Modern China*. Berkeley: University of California Press, 1988.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

Notes: At least if we count the arches for chaste widows as cenotaphs.

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: They usually have a family grave cemetery.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– I don't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

Notes: If we by supreme high god mean Heaven tian 天 it is not, but it is doubtful that

the Confucian notion of Heaven is a supreme high god at all. It has been argued that the translation of tian as Heaven is confusing and that cosmos would be better. Another important concept in Neo-Confucian philosophy is the Supreme Ultimate Taiji 太極, which is not really a high god either. The Neo-Confucian philosopher Zhou Dunyi wrote a diagram of this concept, a diagram called Taijitu 太極圖. Taiji never received sacrifices compared with Heaven, which received offerings from the Emperor. In popular religion and in Daoism the Jade Emperor or the Jade Sovereign Yuhuang Dadi 玉環大地 has a prominent role, and in mythology he is the head of the pantheon. Compared with Heaven and the Supreme Ultimate, the Jade Emperor is anthropomorphic. However, it is important to bear in mind that he is not the creator of the world and he does not have a very important role in Neo-Confucian philosophy and practice. The Neo-Confucians used the Book of Change in their divination practices and as for sacrifices the ancestors and natural gods were the receivers of sacrificial objects.

Reference: Richey, Jeffrey L.. Teaching Confucianism. Oxford University Press, 2008.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=w8vSE2IN0H4C>. p.55-82

Reference: Clart, Philip. "Yuhuang 玉皇 Jade Sovereign; Jade Emperor". Edited by Fabrizio Pregadio. The Encyclopedia of Taoism 2 (n.d.).

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: If we regard the highest god as Heaven, he is a sky deity. Heaven is the ruler of the Dao. Next to Heaven in hierarchy we have the Earth. The sun and the moon are also principal gods. Under them in rank, we have the stars, clouds, winds, rain, thunder, and also gods of mountains, rivers and seas.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Notes: The God of Hell King Yama or Yanwang 閻王, although important, can hardly be regarded as a supreme high god.

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: The emperor is regarded as the son of Heaven but has not the same dignity as Heaven itself.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

Notes: The emperor rules thanks to the mandate of Heaven. If there are uprisings or natural catastrophes it is a sign that the emperor lost the Heavenly mandate.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– No

Notes: There are no statements of the morality of Heaven but a common belief is that Heaven will punish those who act in immoral ways.

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: Heaven does not seem to engage in the affairs of the individual. Still, Heaven has the ultimate power to decide about the fate of all human beings.

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– I don't know

Notes: My impression is that Heaven is not engaged in small matters of the individual. He, however, knows about the behavior of the Emperor, that is, his son.

- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - I don't know
- ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - I don't know
- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - I don't know
- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - I don't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - I don't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Notes: There are a great number of spirits and gods which are worshiped.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– No

Notes: Not directly, only indirectly through natural phenomena, popular uprisings and so on.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

Notes: The followers of Wang Yangming regarded the question of life and death as one of the most important - if not the most important of them all. To be poised for death is the ultimate goal for them, which meant to be in a state of mind without disturbances. They do not, however, discuss the different souls such as the hun 魂 and po 魄 souls which were commonly believed in. It might be a discrepancy between the scholarly debate and ordinary practitioners of the movement. Since popular beliefs not always are written down, we cannot for sure say that there were not such beliefs among the latter. In the Analects, Confucius advises his disciples to not care about spirits, since they do not yet understand human beings. This had been understood by some scholars as if Confucius did not believe in spirits. However, this is not what he was saying. He said they should keep a distance to them, and that was probably because he regarded them as powerful and dangerous. In his study on Zhu Xi's view of ghosts and spirits, Daniel K. Gardner argues in the same way. Zhu Xi also urged his students to turn their attention to matters of daily life but, despite this, he was deeply engaged in the topic of ghosts, spirits and monsters his whole life (Gardner 1995: 599). In his view, ghosts and spirits were qi 氣 in various states of contraction and expansion. His theories had forerunners in other Neo-Confucian thinkers such as Cheng Yi 程頤 (1033-1107) and Zhang Zai 張載 (1020-77) and even Han dynasty philosophers (Gardner 1995: 600 *Journal of the Americal Oriental Society*). We can assume that the proponents of the LuWang school did not differ much from their ideas.

Reference: Peng, Guoxiang. "Death as the Ultimate Concern in Neo-confucian Tradition". In *Mortality in Traditional Chinese Thought*, edited by Amy Olberding and Ivanhoe J. Philip, 271-96. State University of New York Press, 2011.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Reference: Hansen, Valerie. *Changing Gods in Medieval China, 1127-1276*. Princeton University Press, 2014. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=oREABAAAQBAJ>.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: The proponents of the LuWang-School do not talk about this very often, but I think they to a large extent share the same popular beliefs as others. The fact that dragon-spotting is mentioned in local gazetteers means that well-educated officials believed in it, since it was the local officials who compiled those gazetteers. Belief in dragons is, however, not a distinct feature of the LuWang-School. In general people believed in all kinds of gods and spirits. The spirits could be related to natural phenomena such as mountains, rivers and so on. They could also be former humans who in their afterlife turn into a spirit or a ghost. An important ancestor spirit could become a more god of greater importance such as the warrior Guan Yu, who became an important god of war. The Taizhou practitioner Jiao Hong believed in him and sacrificed to him at Chongwenmen in Beijing before his examination. Demons were also commonly believed in.

Reference: Brook, Timothy. *The Troubled Empire*. Harvard University Press, 2013. https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Troubled_Empire.html?hl=&id=fGM0EAAAQBAJ.

Reference: ter Haar, Barend J.. *Guan Yu*. Oxford University Press, 2017. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=2Jc4DwAAQBAJ>.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: At least they often appear in people's dreams.

Reference: Hansen, Valerie. *Changing Gods in Medieval China, 1127-1276*. Princeton University Press, 2014. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=oREABAAAQBAJ>.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: For instance, Guan Yu 關羽 or Guandi 關帝 is worshipped in military temples. Wenchang Wang 文昌王 is the god of literature and was worshipped by the literati.

Reference: ter Haar, Barend J.. *Guan Yu*. Oxford University Press, 2017. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=2Jc4DwAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Lopez, Donald S.. *Religions of China in Practice*. Princeton University Press, 2021. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=OJkvEAAAQBAJ>.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: There are many examples, but one of them is the God of the Hearth or the Kitchen God, Zaojun 灶君, who dwells in the kitchen and reports to the Jade Emperor Yuhuang Dadi 玉皇大帝 about what is going on in the family. There is also the Spirit of the Gate Menshen, who protects the family from ghosts. The City Gods (or the God of Walls and Moats) Chenghuang shen 城隍神 worked in partnership with the magistrate, who took care of the visible world whereas the City God took care of the invisible world.

Reference: Zito, Angela. "City Gods and Their Magistrates". In *Religions of China in Practice*, edited by Donald S. Lopez Jr., 72–81. Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1996.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: More prominent deities have this unrestricted knowledge. Local deities decide in the local area, whereas Heaven (or the Jade Emperor) are believed to dominate the whole universe. Lower spiritual beings cannot harm people without the authorization of Heaven, who even stands above Earth.

Reference: Degroot, J.J.M.. "“universalistic Animism, Polydemonism” in the Religion of the Chinese (p. 18)". Syracuse, New York: The Mason-Henry Press, n.d..

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: At least it is very likely that the malevolent ghosts who dwell in the darkness can see people in the dark.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: Especially Heaven cannot be cheated.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: And if one would like to know about one's destiny, one can always consult the Yijing or engage in other forms of divinatory techniques.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Reference: De Groot, Jan Jakob Maria. *The Religion of the Chinese*. CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform, 2016.

https://books.google.com/books/about/J_J_M_de_Groot_the_Religion_of_the_Chine.html?hl=&id=yjc6MQAACAAJ.

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

Notes: This is probably true.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: They can be very angry, both rightly and wrongly. The deity Guan Di, for instance, expresses anger of righteousness.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Dead ancestors, who are not sacrificed to, or did not receive a proper funeral, can become hungry ghosts (egui 餓鬼). They can also be former human beings who commit sins out of greed.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: The deities are often originally human beings who have been deified.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: It is quite common that human beings are deified after death, or some time after their death. For instance, the general Guan Yu who died in 220 at the end of the Eastern Han dynasty became an important deity whose roles shifted during the later Chinese history. One of his most well-known roles is his role as a war deity.

Reference: ter Haar, Barend J.. Guan Yu. Oxford University Press, 2017.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=2Jc4DwAAQBAJ>.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, and they are seen in the dreams.

Reference: Hansen, Valerie. Changing Gods in Medieval China, 1127-1276. Princeton University Press, 2014. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=oREABAAAQBAJ>.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: Some spirits/gods could take human form and could even have sexual intercourse with human beings. For instance, Wutong 五通 (who was five spirits) seduced women by enticing with gold and silver. Some female mediums had seances for dispelling frights where they had sexual intercourse with those deities. Those who were scared of them bribed them with sacrifices, something which the representatives of the state usually disapproved of. Richard von Glahn, sketches a change of the Wutong spirits' character from malevolent ghosts to benevolent deities throughout Chinese history. The Lu-Wang practitioners relation to such practices is unclear. Most likely, they shared the fear of them as other people did.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Reference: von Glahn, Richard. The Sinister Way. University of California Press, 2004.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=iyvBvYoIZmsC>.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can reward:
– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can punish:
– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:
– Yes
Notes: If the spirits are malevolent they do, and that depends in turn on how they died, the funeral rituals, and later sacrifices.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:
– Yes
Notes: Not only negative emotions. There are demons who harm people in multiple ways.
Reference: von Glahn, Richard. *The Sinister Way*. University of California Press, 2004.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=iyvBvYolZmsC>.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:
– Yes
Notes: This is a very common type of ghost, so-called, hungry ghosts (egui 惡鬼). It is important to feed them to pacify them. If funerals and sacrifices to dead relatives are not conducted properly, they might turn into hungry ghosts.
Reference: von Glahn, Richard. *The Sinister Way*. University of California Press, 2004.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=iyvBvYolZmsC>.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– I don't know

↳ In dreams:
– Yes

Notes: This is the most common way of communication among the Lu-Wang

practitioners.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: I have, however, never encountered that the Lu-Wang practitioners took part in such rituals.

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: I would assume that even the Lu-Wang practitioners consulted the spirits through divination for important decisions in life such as dates for weddings, places of grave shrines and so on.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– I don't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Reference: Hansen, Valerie. *Changing Gods in Medieval China, 1127-1276*. Princeton University Press, 2014. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=oREABAAQBAJ>.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Notes: According to Confucian scriptures such as the Analects one should worship one's own ancestor. To worship ancestors of others is flattery. This statement is reiterated by Zhu Xi. Disputes between the Cheng-Zhu School and the Lu-Wang School never mention that they disagree in this regard.

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: The highest god, that is, Heaven and Earth are worshiped by the emperor, city gods and other major divinities by local officials, and kitchen, house gate gods and minor divinities by ordinary citizens. This hierarchy is legally enforced.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: Several deities are linked to a certain place such as mountains and rivers, others are linked to a domain of trade or occupation, such as the goddess Mazu who is worshiped by fishermen and seafarer. A god can have a more overarching power. The Bodhisattva Guanyin can be worshiped by anyone who suffer in some respect, but she is also especially helpful if one is asking for fertility (of oneself, cattle, crops and so on).

Reference: Yü, Chün-fang. Kuan-yin. Columbia University Press, 2001.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=TtIEr3tod18C>.

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– I don't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The Jade Emperor examines the registers of good and bad deeds. He sends demons to deport sinners from this world, but the god of literati, Wenchang, saves those who are able to reform morally by spirit-writing. Those ideas are usually regarded as Daoist but might be encompassed by Neo-Confucians.

Reference: Goossaert, Vincent. "Modsern Daoist Eschatology: Spirit-writing and Elite Soteriology in Late Imperial China". *Daoism: Religion, History and Society* 6 (n.d.).

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Reference: Goossaert, Vincent. "The Beef Taboo and the Sacrificial Structure of Late Imperial China". In *Of Tripod and Palate: Food, Politics and Religion in Traditional China*, edited by Roel Sterckx, 237–48. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2015.

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: They for instance care about the beef taboo. An example during the reign of

emperor Zhenzhong (998-1022) was a celestial god that took possession of a commoner and those who had eaten beef were struck by misfortune.

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: In Chinese tradition there are ideas about Feng Shui, which is a set of principles for how buildings and grave sites should be arranged. It can, for instance, be that the main gate should face south and water whereas the backside of a building should be towards the north and mountains. This means that there are injunctions and that you should not do the opposite. The imperial palace was a forbidden space for commoners and those who are not invited.

Reference: Huang, E. Y.. "Comparing the Do's & Taboos in Chinese Feng-shui and Indian Vastu-shastra Architectural Traditions". Doctoral thesis, Leiden University, 2012.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: There are a great number of sacred objects in the Confucian tradition and they are used by the proponents of the Lu-Wang School as well. General objects used are incense, incense burners, ancestral tablets, books, specific clothes and so on. The activities in the private academies did not only consist of lectures and discussion, there was also song accompanied by instruments and the gatherings were usually concluded by a drinking ceremony. In the material on the Taizhou movement, there are drawings of bells and drums as well as (wine) vessels and spoons. In the Analects it is said that Zengzi, the disciple of Confucius, played the zither and that Confucius were good at striking the musical stones. Such descriptions served as pattern for later rituals. In the spirit-writing seances (fuji 扶箕), they used a specific rod to direct the stick used for writing. In an officials work, "the four treasures of culture" (wenfang sibao 文房四寶) were used. It refers to the brush, inkstick, paper and inkstone. The sacredness of writing and painting make those into holy objects as well.

Reference: Lidén, Johanna. "The Taizhou Movement: Being Mindful in Sixteenth Century China". Dissertation, Stockholm University, 2018. <http://su.diva-portal.org/smash/record.jsf?pid=diva2%3A1258076&dswid=625>.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Imperial taboo names

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: It seems as if the supernatural beings are especially caring about murder or other crimes which is not punished by the official law, that is, when there is an unfair treatment of someone who could not defend him- or herself.

Reference: ter Haar, Barend J.. "A Word for Violence: The Chinese Term Bao 暴". *Journal of Religion and Violence*, 2021.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– I don't know

Notes: I would guess they care even in such situations if the murder is unrighteous.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– I don't know

Notes: Here I would guess they are less inclined to care, and in the case of military campaigns it would be regarded as justified.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: I would think they cared about adultery but for a man it was legitimate to have concubines and I would not think it would be a big problem if he visited prostitutes either. For a women it would, however, be a crime to be unfaithful to her husband and to be a prostitute would give her a weak social position. However, a man who was deeply into the desire of sex could have been possessed by a fox spirit.

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: Probably this was too a question for spiritual beings. However, a question of importance was what was considered to be incest. For a widow, it would be to remarry with a man of the same lineage as her husband. The law became more strict in the Ming and Qing dynasties. In the Tang dynasty, it was only forbidden for a women to remarry someone with whom she shared mourning relationship with.

Reference: Huang, Philip C.C., and Kathryn Bernhardt, eds.. *The History and Theory of Legal Practice in China*. Edited by Philip C.C. Huang and Kathryn Bernhardt. BRILL, 2014. <https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004276444>.

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: In witch accusations, sexual accusations were common. Such accusation could describe how the woman in question had had sexual intercourse with an evil spirit. If NeoConfucian scholars took part in this kind of slander is hard to say. I assume, they sometimes accepted it in their roles as magistrates, judging in different judicial cases.

Reference: von Glahn, Richard. *The Sinister Way*. University of California Press, 2004. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=iyvBvYoIZmsC>.

Reference: BARRETT, T. H.. "*telling Stories: Witchcraft and Scapegoating in Chinese History*". By BAREND J. TER HAAR. [Leiden and Boston: Brill, 2006. X + 378 Pp. \$155.00. ISBN 90-04-14844-2.] 187 (September 2006).

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: Although, there was not an equivalent set of the Biblic ten commandments in the Confucian tradition, it was still not accepted to lie. The gods were involved in the judicial process and people was asked to swear an oath in from of one of them, for example, the city god. Since (Neo)Confucianism and administration as well as the judicial system was overlapping, we can argue that this was a part of the NeoConfucianism and also the Lu'Wang School. The magistrates acted as judges and they were fostered in the NeoConfucian tradition, receiving their status from the examinations on Confucian classics. (See Barend ter Haar. 2006. "Telling Stories: Witchcraft and Scapegoating in Chinese History", p. 121.)

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– I don't know

Notes: They probably do, at least people believed in sorcery and it was fairly common with accusations of sorcery.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: Theft and robbery are crimes that deities care about.

Reference: ter Haar, Barend J.. "A Word for Violence: The Chinese Term Bao 暴". *Journal of Religion and Violence*, 2021.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

Notes: Conversion is not a big issue in China until Christianity enters the scene.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: In spirit-writing cults they talk about acquiring good and bad wealth, which means that one should do business in a fair way.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Disrespect of written words, maltreatment of women, killing animals and so on

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– I don't know

Notes: Sometimes, the adherents are probably quite certain about who is behind a punishment. Ultimately, it is of course Heaven who mete out the punishment

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– I don't know

Notes: As in the answer above, the adherents sometimes are certain about the reason for the punishment but not always.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Notes: The LuWang adherents are not extremely concerned about supernatural punishments. For them it is more important to live according to the norms of the tradition. However, like everybody else in pre-modern China, they believed in that, for instance, funeral rituals had an impact on the afterlife. If such rituals were not done in the correct way, the deceased person would become a hungry ghost.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– I don't know

Notes: The sources does not talk much about how the "hungry ghost" feels, although we can assume they felt hunger. The sources tell more about the harm they cause for the living.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– I don't know

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– Yes

Notes: The Buddhist ideas of karmic retribution and that an animal could be a reborn person, for instance, a grandparent had become a common view in late imperial China.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– I don't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: It can also be madness.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: The belief in karma became common in China no matter if you labeled yourself as a Confucian, Buddhist or Daoist.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: People might not understand the ways of the deities, but that is another matter.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: In general, Confucianism is regarded as not being interested in the afterlife. In the Analects, when the disciple of Confucius asked about death, Confucius answered that if you do not understand life, why bother about death. However, from the Song dynasty onward and especially in the Ming belief in reincarnation becomes very common. They even tried to trace who was reincarnated into whom. This also applied to learned literati scholars.

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Notes: I would not say that they are HIGHLY emphasized but it was a quite common belief.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– I don't know

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
– I don't know

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
– I don't know

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
– Yes

↳ Other [specify]
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
– Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– I don't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
– I don't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
– Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
– Yes

Notes: Reward in this life consists of success in civil service examinations.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: Messianism is not a distinct feature of the Lu-Wang School. Messianism is mainly found outside of the Confucian tradition, in lay Buddhist movements and in Daoism. Since, the lines between Buddhism, Daoism and Confucianism are rather porous it is, however, sometimes difficult to make the distinctions. The Taizhou movement has some messianistic traits but the Taizhou movement in general has traits which are atypical for the Confucian tradition.

Reference: ter Haar, Barend J.. *Practicing Scripture*. University of Hawaii Press, 2014.

<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=8VgEEAAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Goossart, Vincent. "Modern Daoist Eschatology: Spirit-writing and Elite Soteriology in Late Imperial China". *Daoism: Religion, History and Society* 6 (n.d.).

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: Probably even among Neo-Confucians in late imperial China

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The norms are, however, not listed as in the Ten Commandments in Judaism and Christianity or in the Eightfold path in Buddhism. The Neo-Confucian ethic of the Lu-Wang School is closely connected with their idea of self-cultivation. Through self-cultivation, a moral enlightenment could suddenly take place. Wang Yangming was not preoccupied with moral failure. He argued for a unity of knowledge and action. If a person has the right knowledge, he or she will act morally. If a person does not act morally, he or she has not yet achieved the right knowledge.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Notes: The moral ideas of the LuWang adherents are quite similar to those governing the society at large, with the exception of radical groups such as the Taizhou practitioners. For them, to do extraordinary deeds for friends was very important. It could be to fetch bones of a dead friend to bury it in the cemetery back home.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: But a part of self-cultivation was to eliminate all kinds of desires, that is, desire for wealth, honor, sex, and so on.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: On the contrary, they had a wine drinking ceremony.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: It was not a requirement, but they would be encouraged to donate cereals for granaries, land for graves and schools. This was part of welfare projects at the local level.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: They organized community compacts, which included monthly meetings. During those

meetings incense was burned, the members good and bad deeds were announced and recorded.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes they would try their utmost to protect and save friends in danger. It could, for instance, mean to take care of a friend's bones far away and carry them back home. At the time, travelling was a dangerous task. It could furthermore, mean to help someone out of prison.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: At the community compact meetings, the practitioners vowed to live a morally good life.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: It is possible to argue that the NeoConfucians no matter if they advocated ChengZhu or LuWang ideas belonged to the imperial administration and that commoners and especially women were marginalized in society. In the Ming dynasty NeoConfucian learning was opened up for commoners and women thanks to Wang Yangming's urge to spread it to unlearned men and women. The radical followers of Wang Yangming such as the Taizhou practitioners put this into practice. I would, however, not use the word "marginalized" for commoners and women, since they obviously were a large majority of the population.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: Rituals could be rather large and often took place in private academies, which served as retreat places or "monasteries light" as I usually call them. The activities taking place there were lectures by charismatic leaders, discussions on ethical question, incense burning, music, song and collective meditation.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– No

Notes: Nothing was compulsory. It was rather the other way around, that those activities required good economy, possibility to travel long distances to the academies and spend days sometimes months there. Peasants and craftsmen could of course not spend time and money for that kind of trips.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: It is a question of definition of "institutionalized" whether the answer to this question would be yes or no, but they organize famine relief through 'charitable granaries' (yicang 義倉).

Reference: Lidén, Johanna. "Charitable Schools as a Social Welfare Project in the Ming Dynasty". *Ming Qing Yanjiu* 26, no. 1 (2022): 1-29.

Reference: Smith, Joanna Handlin. *The Art of Doing Good*. University of California Press, 2009.
https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Art_of_Doing_Good.html?hl=&id=_w-0X-UGzwgC.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In the case of Neo-Confucians, the religious group and the state/the institution is more or less the same thing.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: Beside the charitable granaries mentioned above, they also contribute 'charitable graves' and 'charitable schools'.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Charitable deeds seem to be available for everyone in need.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– I don't know

Notes: I think that the family/the clan took care of that.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: As I said above, that was something the family took care of and then we are talking about the extended family not a kernel family.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Notes: The 'charitable schools' were for poorer clan members or boys from poor families in general.

Is such education open to both males and females:

– No

Notes: If girls were educated at all, they were taught by private tutors at home. If they were poor, it is very unlikely that they received any education at all.

Reference: Lidén, Johanna. "Charitable Schools as a Social Welfare Project in the Ming Dynasty". *Ming Qing Yanjiu* 26, no. 1 (2022): 1-29.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Notes: As mentioned above, the LuWang School was partly acting via the institutions but also had their own academies where they spread their message.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: The group did not have much of a formal bureaucracy, but the state had and they of course had to interact with it.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: I would guess that they, except for the state bureaucracy, now and then also interacted with Buddhist and Daoist institutions.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Local officials who organized 'charitable granaries' were not necessarily adherents of the LuWang School, but they could be.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– I don't know

Notes: I know that local officials built bridges and took part in other infrastructure projects, so I would assume they also worked with irrigation and flood control.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Water management was organized by local or higher officials and they might have been proponents of the LuWang School or the Cheng-Zhu School.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– I don't know

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: It is the state that levies taxes not the LuWang group.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: This group does not have their own police and they are not more linked to the ordinary police than the ChengZhu Confucians. The police forces are a part of the imperial system.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: The officials were judges and NeoConfucians were often officials no matter if they belonged to the ChengZhu adherents or the LuWang adherents. However, to be an official was always a precarious situation because there were always someone else on a higher level who could punish you, if not an official with a higher position, the emperor could do it. During, the Ming dynasty, when commoners became a part of the LuWang movement, it was important for them to have support from officials. If not they were in a difficult position. A good example is He Xinyin 何心隱 (1517-1579), who criticized the Grand Secretary Zhang Juzheng 張居正 (1525-1582). He Xinyin was imprisoned and killed there. It is still uncertain who did it, if it was an order from Zhang Juzheng or if it was someone who wanted to ingratiate with him, but Zhang Juzheng's hostility towards the discussions in the private academies played a role here.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: As explained above, some of the adherents of the LuWang School were judges within the imperial administration. Others were commoners who tried to avoid persecution, while others like He Xinyin, did not care. He continued to lecture while escaping from place to place.

Reference: Dimberg, Donald. *The Sage and Society: The Life and Thought of Ho Hsin-yin*. Hawaii: University Press of Hawaii, 1987.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: As part of the imperial legal system, they were not against capital punishment. In fact, Wang Yangming himself was a skilled general and captured bandits. He was also engaged in

fighting leaders of boarder people in today's Yunnan Province. If he killed enemies by his own hand or had subjects doing it for him is hard to say.

Reference: Shin, Leo. "The Last Campaigns of Wang Yangming" 92, no. 1 (2006).
<https://doi.org/10.1163/156853206778553225>.

Reference: Katz, Paul R.. "Timothy Brook, Jérôme Bourgon, Gregory Blue, Death by a Thousand Cuts" 2009, no. 4 (December 31, 2009). <https://doi.org/10.4000/chinaperspectives.4944>.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: Exile was a rather common method to deal with officials with the "wrong" ideas. The method seems, however, have been more common against the LuWang followers, than by them. The reason might be that some of them were radicals, and the ChengZhu followers were in power for longer periods.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Notes: Corporal punishment was common, such as beatings with a bamboo stick. Wang Yangming was beaten by the "heavy bamboo", that is, 100 strokes with a bamboo stick, lost consciousness and was imprisoned. This happened before Wang Yangming was exiled.

Reference: Lidén, Johanna. "The Pedagogical Philosophy of a Village Schoolteacher in Nineteenth-century Sichuan". In *Religions and Local Society in the Historical, Comparative, and Theoretical Perspectives: A Festschrift in Honour of Timothy Brook*. Singapore, 2023.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Notes: That kind of persecution was not institutionalized although it happened.

Reference: ter Haar, Barend. *Figurines, Familiars and Demons: The Fear of Witchcraft and Witches in Imperial China*. forthcoming: forthcoming, n.d..

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Notes: The officials were sent out with their families and servants for a position somewhere in the empire. They was given a residence but that was not their own property. The way to punish an official was to demote him or send him in exile, usually not taking his property, although the emperor confiscated the property of the Grand secretary Zhang Juzheng 張居正 (1525-1582). See Ray Huang, 2008, p. 528.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: As mentioned previously, more radical parts of the LuWang School were persecuted by the authorities and the state. At other times, they belonged to the state. For instance, Wang Yangming himself was a governor and thus a high official.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: Exile was a rather common punishment for "misbehaving" administrators and officials. This happened Wang Yangming after having petitioned in favor of several imprisoned officials. This also happened to other followers of the LuWang School and also officials belonging to other NeoConfucian groups.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Notes: Corporal punishment was common, such as beatings with a bamboo stick. Wang Yangming was beaten by the "heavy bamboo", that is, 100 strokes with a bamboo stick, lost consciousness and was imprisoned. This happened before Wang Yangming was exiled.

Reference: Ching, Julia. *To Acquire Wisdom: The Way of Wang Yang-ming*. New York: Columbia University Press, 1976.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Notes: Ostracism is usually not a measure taken by an institution. However, from another point of view, we could regard the prohibition against girls and women to participate in civil service examination and having a position within the imperial administration as a kind of extreme form of institutionalized ostracism.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They are subject to the legal code of the empire.

Reference: Huang, Ray. "'the Lung-ching and Wan-li Reigns 1567-1620" , In: *The Cambridge History of China Online Version Vol 7, the Ming Dynasty 1368-1644*". Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2008.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Officials such as Wang Yangming were military officials. On a lower level, there were adherents of more popular movements within the Wang Yangming movement who were ordinary soldiers.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They should at least be protected against bandits, rebels, and invading armies by the military.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: It is, however, possible to argue that the Classical Chinese was the language of the NeoConfucians as an elite language, compared with the vernacular of commoners.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: They follow the traditional Chinese calendar 'nongli' 農曆. There were also specific calendars for rituals.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Like other philanthropic officials they built up charitable granaries.

Reference: Lidén, Johanna. "Charitable Schools as a Social Welfare Project in the Ming Dynasty". *Ming Qing Yanjiu* 26, no. 1 (2022): 1-29.

Reference: Smith, Joanna Handlin. *The Art of Doing Good*. University of California Press, 2009.
https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Art_of_Doing_Good.html?hl=&id=_w-0X-UGzwgC.

Bibliography

General References

Reference: The LuWang School, the School of Lu Xiangshan and Wang Yangming, De Groot, Jan Jakob Maria. *The Religion of the Chinese*. CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform, 2016.
https://books.google.com/books/about/J_J_M_de_Groot_the_Religion_of_the_Chine.html?hl=&id=yjc6MQAACAAJ.

Reference: The LuWang School, the School of Lu Xiangshan and Wang Yangming, Ivanhoe, P. J.. *Confucian Moral Self Cultivation*. Hackett Publishing, 2000.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Confucian_Moral_Self_Cultivation.html?hl=&id=W7XRfHzoUt8C.

Reference: The LuWang School, the School of Lu Xiangshan and Wang Yangming, Ivanhoe, P. J.. *Ethics in the Confucian Tradition*. Hackett Publishing, 2002.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Ethics_in_the_Confucian_Tradition.html?hl=&id=Sf9kpJ72hJMC.

Reference: The LuWang School, the School of Lu Xiangshan and Wang Yangming, Olberding, Amy. *Mortality in Traditional Chinese Thought*. SUNY Press, 2012. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=gBW5bCFYRh8C>.

Reference: The LuWang School, the School of Lu Xiangshan and Wang Yangming, Peng, Guoxiang. "Death as the Ultimate Concern in Neo-confucian Tradition: Wang Yangming's Followers as an Example". In *Mortality in Traditional Chinese Thought*, 271-96. Albany, NY: State University of New York Press, 2011.

Reference: The LuWang School, the School of Lu Xiangshan and Wang Yangming, Hsi, Chu. *Chu Hsi's Family Rituals*. Princeton University Press, 2016.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Chu_Hsi_s_Family_Rituals.html?hl=&id=QFVjwEACAAJ.

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Source 1: Ching, Julia, 1976, *To Acquire Wisdom: the Way of Wang Yang-ming*., Source 2: Chan, Wing-tsit, 1963, *A Sourcebook in Chinese Philosophy*., Source 3: Lü, Miao-fen 呂妙芬, 2010 , *Yangmingxue shi ren shequn; Lishi, Sixiang yu Shijian 陽明學士人社群- 歷史、思想與實踐*., Ivanhoe, Philip J.. *Readings from the Lu-wang School of Neo-confucianism*. Hackett Publishing, 2009.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=Wk2dT22o19gC>.

Reference: Source 1: Ching, Julia, 1976, *To Acquire Wisdom: the Way of Wang Yang-ming*., Source 2: Chan, Wing-tsit, 1963, *A Sourcebook in Chinese Philosophy*., Source 3: Lü, Miao-fen 呂妙芬, 2010 , *Yangmingxue shi ren shequn; Lishi, Sixiang yu Shijian 陽明學士人社群- 歷史、思想與實踐*., Yao, Xinzhong, and Hsin-chung Yao. *An Introduction to Confucianism*. Cambridge University Press, 2000.
https://books.google.com/books/about/An_Introduction_to_Confucianism.html?hl=&id=tAE2OJ9bPG0C.

Reference: Yes, Yü, Chün-fang. Kuan-yin. Columbia University Press, 2001.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=TtIEr3tod18C>.

Reference: Yes, ter Haar, Barend J.. *Guan Yu*. Oxford University Press, 2017.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=2Jc4DwAAQBAJ> , ,

Reference: Yes, De Groot, Jan Jakob Maria. *The Religion of the Chinese*. CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform, 2016.
https://books.google.com/books/about/J_J_M_de_Groot_the_Religion_of_the_Chine.html?hl=&id=yjc6MQAACAAJ.

Reference: No, Peng, Guoxiang. "Death as the Ultimate Concern in Neo-confucian Tradition". In *Mortality in Traditional Chinese Thought*, edited by Amy Olberding and Ivanhoe J. Philip, 271-96. State University of New York Press, 2011.

Reference: Yes, Brook, Timothy. *The Troubled Empire*. Harvard University Press, 2013.
https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Troubled_Empire.html?hl=&id=fGM0EAAAQBAJ.

Reference: Yes, Lopez, Donald S.. *Religions of China in Practice*. Princeton University Press, 2021.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=OJkvEAAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Yes, Zito, Angela. "City Gods and Their Magistrates". In *Religions of China in Practice*, edited by Donald S. Lopez Jr., 72-81. Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1996.

Reference: No, Richey, Jeffrey L.. *Teaching Confucianism*. Oxford University Press, 2008.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=w8vSE2IN0H4C>. p.55-82

Reference: Yes, Hansen, Valerie. *Changing Gods in Medieval China, 1127-1276*. Princeton University Press, 2014. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=oREABAAAQBAJ> , , ,

Reference: Yes [specify]: In witch accusations, sexual accusations were common. Such accusation could describe how the woman in question had had sexual intercourse with an evil spirit. If NeoConfucian scholars took part in this kind of slander is hard to say. I assume, they sometimes accepted it in their roles as magistrates, judging in different judicial cases., von Glahn, Richard. *The Sinister Way*. University of California Press, 2004. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=iyvBvYoIZmsC> , , ,

Reference: No, ter Haar, Barend J.. *Practicing Scripture*. University of Hawaii Press, 2014.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=8VgEEAAAQBAJ>.

Reference: No, Goossart, Vincent. "Modern Daoist Eschatology: Spirit-writing and Elite Soteriology in Late Imperial China". *Daoism: Religion, History and Society* 6 (n.d.).

Reference: Yes, Goossaert, Vincent. "Modsern Daoist Eschatology: Spirit-writing and Elite Soteriology in Late Imperial China". *Daoism: Religion, History and Society* 6 (n.d.).

Reference: No, Clart, Philip. "Yuhuang 玉皇 Jade Sovereign; Jade Emperor". Edited by Fabrizio Pregadio. *The Encyclopedia of Taoism 2* (n.d.).

Reference: Yes, Goossaert, Vincent. "The Beef Taboo and the Sacrificial Structure of Late Imperial China". In *Of Tripod and Palate: Food, Politics and Religion in Traditional China*, edited by Roel Sterckx, 237-48. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2015.

Reference: Yes, Huang, E. Y.. "Comparing the Do's & Taboos in Chinese Feng-shui and Indian Vastu-shastra Architectural Traditions". Doctoral thesis, Leiden University, 2012.

Reference: Yes, Lidén, Johanna. "The Taizhou Movement: Being Mindful in Sixteenth Century China". Dissertation, Stockholm University, 2018. <http://su.diva-portal.org/smash/record.jsf?pid=diva2%3A1258076&dswid=625>.

Reference: Yes, Lidén, Johanna. "Charitable Schools as a Social Welfare Project in the Ming Dynasty". *Ming Qing Yanjiu* 26, no. 1 (2022): 1-29. , ,

Reference: No, Smith, Joanna Handlin. *The Art of Doing Good*. University of California Press, 2009. https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Art_of_Doing_Good.html?hl=&id=_w-0X-UGzwc. ,

Reference: Yes, ter Haar, Barend J.. "A Word for Violence: The Chinese Term Bao 暴". *Journal of Religion and Violence*, 2021. ,

Reference: Yes, Huang, Philip C.C., and Kathryn Bernhardt, eds.. *The History and Theory of Legal Practice in China*. Edited by Philip C.C. Huang and Kathryn Bernhardt. BRILL, 2014. <https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004276444>.

Reference: Yes [specify]: In witch accusations, sexual accusations were common. Such accusation could describe how the woman in question had had sexual intercourse with an evil spirit. If NeoConfucian scholars took part in this kind of slander is hard to say. I assume, they sometimes accepted it in their roles as magistrates, judging in different judicial cases., BARRETT, T. H.. "*telling Stories: Witchcraft and Scapegoating in Chinese History*". By BAREND J. TER HAAR. [Leiden and Boston: Brill, 2006. X + 378 Pp. \$155.00. ISBN 90-04-14844-2.] 187 (September 2006). <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0305741006410420>.

Reference: No, Dimberg, Donald. *The Sage and Society: The Life and Thought of Ho Hsin-yin*. Hawaii: University Press of Hawaii, 1987.

Reference: Yes, Shin, Leo. "The Last Campaigns of Wang Yangming" 92, no. 1 (2006). <https://doi.org/10.1163/156853206778553225>.

Reference: Yes, Lidén, Johanna. "The Pedagogical Philosophy of a Village Schoolteacher in Nineteenth-century Sichuan". In *Religions and Local Society in the Historical, Comparative, and Theoretical Perspectives: A Festschrift in Honour of Timothy Brook*. Singapore , 2023.

Reference: Yes, Katz, Paul R.. "Timothy Brook, Jérôme Bourgon, Gregory Blue, Death by a Thousand Cuts" 2009, no. 4 (December 31, 2009). <https://doi.org/10.4000/chinaperspectives.4944>.

Reference: No, ter Haar, Barend. *Figurines, Familiars and Demons: The Fear of Witchcraft and Witches in Imperial China*. forthcoming: forthcoming, n.d..

Reference: Yes, Ching, Julia. *To Acquire Wisdom: The Way of Wang Yang-ming*. New York: Columbia University Press, 1976.

Reference: Yes, Rawski, Evelyn S.. "'the Imperial Way of Death", In: *Death Ritual in Late Imperial and Modern China*". Berkeley: University of California Press, 1988.

Reference: Yes, Degroot, J.J.M.. "'universalistic Animism, Polydemonism" in the Religion of the Chinese (p.

18)". Syracuse, New York: The Mason-Henry Press, n.d..

Reference: Yes, Huang, Ray. "the Lung-ching and Wan-li Reigns 1567-1620" , In: The Cambridge History of China Online Version Vol 7, the Ming Dynasty 1368-1644". Cambrigde: Cambridge University Press, 2008.